

At maturity, 25 random panicles of the main tillers in each variety in each replication were selected for HD grains and their component characters. HD grains were separated by soaking the grains in salt solution with a specific gravity of 1.20. The HD grain index was calculated as a ratio of the number of HD grains to the number of spikelets and expressed in %.

The highest values for GYP, HDGP, and HDIP were noted in KAU-MO-1-80 (see table). TKM 9, which had relatively higher

HDGP and HDIP, had lower GYP because of lesser grain weight. MO 7 and MO 8, which had lesser HDIP, had higher GYP because of more HDGP. In general, HDISB was lower than HDIPB; this was more pronounced in varieties MO 7, MO 8, and MO 9, which had lower HDIP. These results revealed that HDIP, which was mostly decided by HDISB and HDGPB, could be increased by higher HDGSB. Thus, the possibility of enhancing yield potential exists in MO 7, MO 8, and MO 9.

A wider variation was noted for secondary branches as well as HDGSB than for primary branches and HDGPB. GYP was strongly and positively correlated with HDGP, secondary branches, and HDGSB. In turn, HDGP had a strong positive correlation with HDGSB and secondary branches. The study suggests that to increase the number of HD grains panicle⁻¹ (and thereby yield level), plants with more secondary branches panicle⁻¹ and more HD grains on these branches should be selected.

High-density (HD) grain and its component characters in five rice varieties, 1997 kharif, Karaikal, India.

Character ^a	MO 7	MO 8	MO 9	KAU-MO-1-80	TKM 9	Mean	CD (5%)	r ^b with HDGP	r with GYP
PB	11.90	12.05	10.70	11.80	8.45	10.98	0.89	0.28	0.62**
SB	23.75	31.90	19.15	33.40	22.80	26.20	5.63	0.77**	0.87**
HDGPB	53.38	51.80	47.85	66.65	50.40	54.02	7.08	0.64**	0.77**
HDGSB	48.15	64.85	27.55	81.65	61.15	56.67	10.22	0.98**	0.84**
HDIPB	80.35	74.23	73.40	92.53	88.90	81.88	8.48	0.58**	0.32**
HDISB	65.45	54.25	46.05	81.05	86.17	66.60	10.35	0.64**	0.32
HDIP	72.20	62.05	60.05	88.83	86.20	73.86	10.32	0.62**	0.28
HDGP	101.53	116.65	75.40	148.30	111.55	110.68	14.35	-0.87**	
GYP	3.34	3.53	2.24	3.86	2.71	3.13	0.22	--	

^aPB = number of primary branches panicle⁻¹, SB = number of secondary branches panicle⁻¹, HDGPB = number of HD grains on PB, HDGSB = number of HD grains on SB, HDIPB = HD grain index on PB, HDISB = HD grain index on SB, HDIP = HD grain index panicle⁻¹, HDGP = HD grains panicle⁻¹, and GYP = grain yield panicle⁻¹.
^br = simple correlation coefficient. **Significant at P = 0.01.

KDML 105, an alternative aromatic rice for the semideepwater ecosystem

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About 77% of ricelands in Assam are annually submerged for 2-10 d or more due to rain and flood in the wet season. The predominant winter rice (Sali) is often inundated from 50 to 200 cm, resulting in extensive damage to the crop. The semideepwater rice grown in the lower regions can tolerate submergence, but the yield and cooking qualities of the kernels are lower than those of Mahsuri. Mahsuri is a popular winter rice. Joha, a group of wet-season rice varieties grown on upland

to medium land, which cannot withstand submergence, is well-known for its strong aroma, superfine grain, and excellent cooking quality. But Joha's productivity is only 2-3 t ha⁻¹.

We introduced KDML 105, a native, aromatic semideepwater rice of Thailand, in Assam during 1995 from an international germplasm exchange program of IRRI. KDML stands for "Khao Dawk Mali" in Thai, meaning Jasmine white kernel. KDML 105 can withstand 50-80 cm submergence,

stands erect until maturity, flowers by the end of October, and can be grown as direct-seeded semideepwater rice or as wet-season winter rice in Assam.

Table 1 shows the yields of KDML 105 from 1995 to 1997 over 14 locations in five districts of Assam. KDML 105 had a pooled average mean yield of 4.2 t ha⁻¹ over years and locations, with 33% more yield than local semideepwater variety Panikekoa, and 51% more than the best Joha variety—Kolajoha.

In 1993, KDML 105 was tested under the 16th International Rainfed Lowland Rice Observational Nursery of INGER as accession no. ET23263 (IRRI, Philippines).

KDML 105 is photoperiod-sensitive and may be harvested with other winter rice varieties. It has been recommended for cultivation in semideepwater ecosystems in the North Bank Plain Zone of Assam in 1998. KDML 105 exhibited moderate tolerance for major rice diseases. The incidence of rice stem borers and rice hispa in KDML 105 was more than that in Kolajoha and Panikekoa (14.4% stem and 4.6% leaf damage by stem borers and hispa, respectively). Under 8 mo of storage, KDML 105 exhibited 11% damage in grains due to rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. Kernel softness and aroma may have attracted the insects in storage.

KDML 105 has slender grains of 9.8 × 2.8-mm dimensions and a 1000-grain weight of 25.3 g (Table 2). The kernels are soft and off-white and have a strong aroma. In an organoleptic test, 80% of a panel thought that KDML 105 was equivalent to the best Joha variety of Assam, 30% thought it was superior to Joha, and 35% said it was equivalent to Mahsuri. Cooked KDML 105 is sticky and 75% thought that the variety is unique and excellent for rice dishes such as polao, kheer, and frumenty.

KDML 105 is fast expanding in the semideepwater ecosystem as scented winter rice in Assam.

Table 1. Yield of KDML 105, Kolajoha, and Panikekoa in Assam, India, 1995-97.

Year	Location	District	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
			KDML 105	Kolajoha	Panikekoa
1995	Garumuria	Lakhimpur	3.4	2.4	1.8
	Gharmora	Lakhimpur	6.0	3.0	-
1996	Garumuria 1	Lakhimpur	3.0	2.2	2.8
	Garumuria 2	Lakhimpur	4.4	2.6	2.5
	Garumuria 3	Lakhimpur	1.9	-	0.9
	Gharmora	Lakhimpur	3.5	2.7	-
	Kuwari-Pukhuri	Jorhat	5.4	3.1	-
	Borigaon	Jorhat	5.8	3.0	-
1997	Dhemaji	Dhemaji	4.4	-	4.3
	Dhakuakhana	Lakhimpur	4.8	-	4.0
	Garumuria	Lakhimpur	2.8	-	2.4
	Gohpur	Sonitpur	5.4	-	6.0
	Mangaldol	Darrang	2.0	-	3.2
	Gharmora	Lakhimpur	5.2	3.0	-
Pooled av			4.2	2.8	3.1

Table 2. Characteristics of KDML 105, Assam, 1997.

Characteristic	Remarks
<i>Plant</i>	
Type	Tall, nonlodging, semideepwater
Height (cm)	147.0
Photosensitivity	Photoperiod-sensitive
Flowering time	Late October
<i>Duration</i>	
Direct-sown	March-December
Transplanted	June-December
<i>Panicle</i>	
Type	Compact
Length (cm)	24.7
Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	180.6
Sterility (%)	17.2
<i>Grains</i>	
Length (mm)	9.8
Breadth (mm)	2.8
L/B	3.6
Test weight (g, 1000 seeds ⁻¹)	25.3
<i>Yield (t ha⁻¹)</i>	
Direct-seeded	1.9-3.5
Transplanted	3.0-6.0

Sudhir, a progeny of FR13A

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FR13A was identified as an excellent source of submergence tolerance (HilleRisLambers et al 1986). It has been used by many breeders for transferring

submergence tolerance gene(s) into modern varieties. Sudhir is perhaps the first variety that used FR13A as a parent; it was developed from the cross FR13A/Biraj at

the RRS in 1981. The male parent, Biraj, an X-ray mutant of OC 1393 released in 1982, has very good regeneration capacity, good grain quality, tolerance for